

One-pot syntheses and characterizations of $[\text{Cd}(\text{diik})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ [diik = *N,N'*-carbonyldiimidazole] and $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ [imH = imidazole] : 2D supramolecular sheet structure in $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ through N–H...O hydrogen bonds

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Abstract : The details of synthesis and characterization of two mononuclear coordination compounds $[\text{Cd}(\text{diik})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (1) [diik = *N,N'*-carbonyldiimidazole] and $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (2) [imH = imidazole] are described. The compounds are characterized on the basis of microanalytical, spectroscopic and physicochemical results. Structure of 2 has been solved by X-ray diffraction measurement. Structural analysis shows that cadmium(II) centre in 2 has a centrosymmetric octahedral geometry with a CdN_6 chromophore ligated through six N atoms of six imH ligands. The mononuclear units in 2 are packed through N–H...O hydrogen bonds leading to a 2D sheet structure in *ac* plane. Compounds 1 and 2 display intraligand $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ fluorescence at room temperature.

Keywords : Cadmium(II), imidazole, synthesis, superstructure, luminescence.

Introduction

Metal-organic frameworks (MOF's) with varied complex molecular and crystalline architectures¹⁻³ are extensively studied for their interesting chemical and physical properties and potential applications as functional materials⁴⁻⁷. One-pot synthesis⁸ of the building components is one of the efficient synthetic approaches to construct such topologies based on strong metal-ligand covalent bond⁹ and multiple weak non-covalent forces like hydrogen bonds^{10,11}. Imidazole¹² (imH) is a versatile terminal/bridging ligand and the interest in its chemistry emanates from its use as ionic liquid¹³ and from biological and pharmacological activities¹⁴. The active hydrogen present in the imH moiety can act as hydrogen bond donor with active -NH- hydrogen to generate different supramolecular architectures^{12,15}. *N,N'*-Carbonyldiimidazole (diik) with two im units bridged by carbonyl group has been the centre of attraction by coordination chemists to prepare different compounds of chemical interest^{16,17}. Recently we are active¹⁸⁻²¹ to prepare different metal-organic frameworks by changing metal ion geometry setters, organic blockers with tailored arms

and inorganic/organic bridges with multiple connectors. The present work stems from our interest on the reaction behaviour of *N,N'*-carbonyldiimidazole (diik) towards preparation of ligand bridged polymeric ensembles in combination with metal(II) pseudohalides. Recently, we reported²¹ its reaction behaviour to a 3d metal ion viz. manganese(II). To extend this to a 4d ion, here we have examined its behaviour to cadmium(II). A 1 : 3 molar ratio of cadmium(II) perchlorate and diik results in tris complex of the type $[\text{Cd}(\text{diik})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (1). But once again carbonyl bridge cleavage of diik occurs in presence of the pseudohalides like azide, thiocyanate and cyanate resulting dicationic hexacoordinated cadmium(II) compound $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (2) which is structurally characterized. Direct reaction of the cadmium(II) salt with imH results in 2 in high yield. The syntheses, characterizations, structures and luminescence behaviour of these two new coordination compounds are described here.

Results and discussion

A 1 : 3 molar ratio of the cadmium(II) salt and the bidentate organic ligand diik resulted in $[\text{Cd}(\text{diik})_3]^{2+}$ as shown in eq. (1). But with 1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratios of metal salt, diik and pseudohalide (X) such as N_3^- , NCS^- and NCO^- , bridge cleavage reaction of diik occurred leading to mononuclear imidazole coordination compound $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6]^{2+}$ in low yield and no pseudohalide compound was formed [eq. (2)]. Direct reaction of imH with cadmium(II) salt in the molar ratio 1 : 6 afforded $[\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(\text{imH})_6]^{2+}$ [eq. (3)] :

Both the compounds were characterized by elemental analyses, electrical conductivities, IR, UV-Vis and luminescence spectra. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with formulations 1 and 2. The air-stable, moisture-insensitive coordination compounds are powders, soluble in a range of common organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, acetonitrile, but are insoluble in water. In MeOH solutions both behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes²² as reflected in their conductivity values ($\Lambda_{\text{M}} = 230$ and $240 \text{ } \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for 1 and 2, respectively). In IR, $\nu(\text{ClO}_4)$ stretches at ~ 1090 and $\sim 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are invariably seen. A relatively weak band at $\sim 3070 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assignable to $\nu(\text{CH})$ mode of aromatic imidazole/diik unit. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretch of diik in 1 is seen at 1685 cm^{-1} . A broad band of $\nu(\text{NH})$ centered at 3190 cm^{-1} is indicative of $\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}$ hydrogen bonding in 2. In MeOH solutions, the free ligands imH and diik show absorptions respectively at 240 nm ($\epsilon, 4070 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 245 nm ($\epsilon, 5780 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which may involve $n\text{-}\pi^*/\pi\text{-}\pi^*$

Fig. 1. An ORTEP diagram of $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6]^{2+}$ with atom labelling scheme and 20% probability ellipsoids for all non hydrogen atoms.

transition. The coordination compounds 1 and 2 exhibit intense absorption bands at 312 nm ($\epsilon, 7340 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 314 nm ($\epsilon, 6120 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) assignable to intraligand $n\text{-}\pi^*/\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition. Reflectance spectra [λ_{max} (nm), 312 (1), 314 (2)] in nujol and electronic spectra in MeOH solutions are akin reflecting gross geometric and electronic structures in solid state and in solution. Upon photoexcitation at 312 nm of 1 and at 314 nm of 2 in MeOH solutions at room temperature intense fluorescence bands were observed with a maximum respectively at 350 nm and 382 nm assignable to intraligand $^1(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence²³.

A thermal ellipsoid plot with atom numbering scheme of the compound 2 is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond distances and bond angles relevant to metal coordination sphere in the monomer are given in Table 2. Significant hydrogen bonding data are set in Table 3. The crystal lattice of 2 consists of $[\text{Cd}(\text{imH})_6]^{2+}$ cations and ClO_4^- anions. The cadmium(II) centre adopts a distorted octahedral geometry with a CdN_6 chromophore. Six nitrogen atoms [N(1), N(3), N(5), N(1*), N(3*) and N(5*)] of imidazole moiety completes the coordination sphere around the metal centre. The equatorial positions are occupied by N(3), N(5), N(3*) and N(5*), and N(1)

and N(1*) are placed in the axial positions. The two axial Cd–N [Cd–N(1) and Cd–N(1*)] distances in **2** are same [2.348(3) Å] and in the equatorial plane, each of the Cd–N(3) and Cd–N(3*) distances is 2.365(3) Å and each of Cd–N(5) and Cd–N(5*) distances, 2.375(3) Å. The angles subtended by the monodentate ligand around cadmium(II) centre in the equatorial plane show a significant variation [87.61(9)–92.39(9)°] from the ideal 90°. The trans N(1)–Cd–N(1*) angle is ideal 180°. In the crystal lattice, **2** packs with each other to give a 2D sheet structure (Fig. 2) through multiple N–H...O hydrogen bonds (Table 3) along the *ac* plane. The non-coordinated imidazole N atoms [N(2), N(4) and N(6)] of three different imidazole moieties residing along three different coordination axes act as potential proton donors, whereas O atoms [O(1), O(2) and O(3)] of perchlorate counter anion as proton acceptors [N(2)–H(1)...O(2), 2.59(6) Å, <N(2)–H(1)...O(2), 135.0(4)°; N(2)–H(1)...O(1), 2.45(6) Å, <N(2)–H(1)...O(1), 131.0(4)°; N(4)–H(1)...O(3), 2.19(6) Å, <N(4)–H(1)...O(3), 158.0(5)°; N(6)–H(1)...O(2), 2.20(5) Å, <N(6)–H(1)...O(2), 157.0(5)°; symmetry code : ^a -1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z; ^b -1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z; ^c -x, 1-y, 1-z; ^d 1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z].

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity *N,N'*-carbonyldiimidazole (Lancaster, UK) and sodium azide (Aldrich, USA), ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India), sodium cyanate (Aldrich, USA) were used as received. Cadmium(II) perchlorate hexahydrate was prepared by treatment of cadmium(II) carbonate (E. Merck, India) with perchloric acid (E. Merck, India) followed by slow evaporation on a steam-bath, filtered through a fine glass-frit, and preserved in a desiccator containing concentrated sulfuric acid (E. Merck, India) for subsequent use. All other chemicals and solvents were AR grade and used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Caution! Perchlorate salts of metal ions are potentially explosive²⁴ especially in presence of organic ligands. Only a small amount of the material should be prepared and handled with care.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for [Cd(imH)₃](ClO₄)₂ (**2**)

Crystallographic parameter	2
Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₁₂ Cl ₂ O ₈ Cd
Formula weight	719.79
Temperature (K)	293 (2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, P21/n
<i>A</i> (Å)	11.8374(7)
<i>B</i> (Å)	7.2551(4)
<i>C</i> (Å)	16.5246(10)
β (°)	90.1150(10)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1419.16(14)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D_c</i> (mg m ⁻³)	1.684
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.022
<i>F</i> (000)	724
θ ranges (°)	3.1, 28.3
<i>h</i> / <i>k</i> / <i>l</i>	-15 : 15; -9 : 9; -21 : 15
Reflections collected	8679
Independent reflections	3482
Completeness to theta	28.30
<i>N_{ref}</i>	3482
<i>N_{var}</i>	235
Data/restraints/parameters	3482/0/235
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> = 0.0411, <i>wR</i> = 0.1048
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.022
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	-0.88, 0.63
$R = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $; $wR = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, Calcd. $w = 1 / [\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0477P)^2 + 1.1370P]$ (2) where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2) / 3$.	

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RX1 FTIR spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solutions and MeOH was used as solvent. UV-Vis (in MeOH) and reflectance spectra were recorded with Jasco UV-Vis-NIR model V-570 spectrometer.

Fig. 2. Perspective view of 2D sheet structure of 2 parallel to *ac*-plane.

Fluorescence measurements were done using Hitachi fluorescence spectrofluorimeter F-4500.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for 2

Bond distances :			
Cd–N(1)	2.348(3)	Cd–N(1*)	2.348(3)
Cd–N(3)	2.365(3)	Cd–N(3*)	2.365(3)
Cd–N(5)	2.375(3)	Cd–N(5*)	2.375(3)
Bond angles :			
N(1)–Cd–N(3)	90.99(9)	N(1)–Cd–N(5)	92.39(9)
N(1)–Cd–N(1*)	180.00	N(1)–Cd–N(3*)	89.01(9)
N(1)–Cd–N(5*)	87.61(9)	N(3)–Cd–N(5)	92.31(9)
N(1*)–Cd–N(3)	89.01(9)	N(3)–Cd–N(3*)	180.00
N(3)–Cd–N(5*)	87.69(9)	N(1*)–Cd–N(5)	87.61(9)
N(3*)–Cd–N(5)	87.69(9)	N(5)–Cd–N(5*)	180.00
N(1*)–Cd–N(3*)	90.99(9)	N(1*)–Cd–N(5*)	92.39(9)
N(3*)–Cd–N(5*)	92.31(9)		

Preparation of complexes :

$[Cd(diik)_3](ClO_4)_2$ (1) : Solid diik (487 mg, 3 mmol) was added slowly to $Cd(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (419 mg, 1 mmol) dissolved in MeOH (20 ml). The solution was filtered through a glass-frit and was kept in air for slow evaporation. After a few days light yellow compound 1 was separated. Yield, 598 mg (75%) (Found : C, 31.47; H, 2.20; N, 21.00. Calcd. $C_{21}H_{18}N_{12}O_{11}Cl_2Cd$ (1) : C, 31.60; H, 2.27; N, 21.09%).

$[Cd(imH)_6](ClO_4)_2$ (2) : This may be prepared in presence of NaN_3 , NH_4SCN or $NaNCO$ and starting with any of the mole ratios 1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 2 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 with respect to the metal ion, diik and pseudohalide. The synthesis with the azide is described here with the mole ratio of 1 : 2 : 1. To a solution of diik (325 mg, 2 mmol) was added slowly to $Cd(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (419 mg, 1 mmol)

Table 3. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for 2

D–H...A	D–H	H...A	D...A	D–H...A
N(2)–H(1)...O(2) ^a	0.86(6)	2.59(6)	3.260(7)	135.0(4)
N(2)–H(1)...O(1) ^b	0.86(6)	2.45(6)	3.080(6)	131.0(4)
N(4)–H(1)...O(3) ^c	0.95(6)	2.19(6)	3.095(5)	158.0(5)
N(6)–H(1)...O(2) ^d	0.74(6)	2.20(5)	2.895(6)	157.0(5)

^a-1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z; ^b-1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z; ^c-x, 1-y, 1-z; ^d1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z.

dissolve in MeOH (15 ml). To the light yellow solution, aqueous solution (5 ml) of NaN_3 (65 mg, 1 mmol) was added drop-wise with stirring. The solution mixture was filtered through a glass-frit and was kept in air for slow evaporation. After a few days light yellow single crystals of **2** suitable for X-ray crystal structural analysis were obtained. Yield, 396 mg (55%). The same product was obtained by applying the 1 : 2 : 2 and 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratios. **2** was also prepared using imH and the metal perchlorate in the molar ratio 1 : 6 in the same solvent mixture. Yield, 576 mg (80%) (Found : C, 30.00; H, 3.32; N, 23.31. Calcd. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{Cd}$ (**2**) : C, 30.03; H, 3.33; N, 23.35%).

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

The X-ray diffraction data were collected and analyzed as reported in our previous publication²¹.

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for CCDC-640050 for **2** has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC). Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12, Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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